

LABELLING, STIGMATISATION AND NOTATION OF THE UNDERLYING VALUE CONVEYED BY AI/T

Brief Considerations on Social Research Aimed at Social Pathology on the WEB

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Abstract

Simmelian social interaction theory, which predates Goffman's theories, highlighted the connection between interaction→sociation→social effects, also identifying the volume of interactions as a key variable in social evolution. This latter, which is generally considered independent of the individual social agent, also explained a pathology: the emergence of the *blasé* type as a defensive reaction to the incessant growth of interactive stimuli. This provides an opportunity to correlate the effect and frequency of social interaction in a stratified, competitive metropolitan context. Making only general reference to the possible effects (deterministic or probabilistic) of *labeling and stigma* on the onset of deviance and mental illness or their outcomes, but simply drawing on general Goffmanian indications, it is assumed that stigmatization of an individual actually triggers social effects, including, for example, social isolation (a precursor to alienation), impacting participation, inclusion, and cohesion. This process can be triggered by a generic social agent who identifies as "rejecting the deviant," subsequently taking on a collective dimension. It should be noted, however, that rejection, in any case, is not the only possible option; there may be positions of acceptance or even indifference. This highlights how the effects of simple interaction itself are not only linked to frequency, but also to the value and significance of the interaction, as well as its specific purposes, which can determine its effects, or at least direct them in an intentionally preordained manner. It can be conceptualized that, in a society or segment of it, stigma arises when two interrelated components are employed: a) human differences are identified and labeled; b) a social agent, usually belonging to the dominant culture, links the labeled individual to negative attributes and/or stereotypes. All this in a metropolitan, computerized, stratified and competitive society can lead to pre-ordained discrimination *ad excludendum* functionally aimed at a desired result according to the *ad imperandum ambitions* of elite classes, severely influencing political, economic, and social choices and even social mobility, to positions pre-established for the purpose of achieving a desired outcome from strategic centers that are not necessarily immediately traceable and locatable. Conversely, labeled and stigmatized potentials are largely always tracked, thanks to the information technology now widespread across every social strata, and can be located in real time. This poses not only problems of asymmetry, precaution, and prevention for social justice, but also genuine security concerns for every social agent, faced with concrete acts of hacking and falsification through *Artificial Intelligence* (AI) systems. This portends social conflicts that find their consummation in cyberspace. The analysis's final invitation is to rediscover the myth of social pathology that was forced and relegated to marginal positions after the past student uprisings and the metropolitan ghettos, phenomena that are similarly resurfacing today. Ultimately, it's about rediscovering a serious critique of the power establishment as a whole, whether autocratic or democratic. Regardless of partisanship, and with firm conviction in its values, the sociologist's mission must assume a critical public role, rather than adhering to pseudo-scientific positions, willing to negotiate the elevation of one's status in exchange for renouncing one's own "ideological apologia." Adopting Goffman's metaphor of theatrical representation, labeling and stigmatization can ultimately be seen as a "public spectacle." This is all the more true as today's highly computerized society of spectacle and consumption is pervaded by artificially intelligent media. Three parties always participate in the "spectacle": a victim, a perpetrator, and an audience. It is played out publicly, before the eyes of a territorialized and localized audience, dispersed across its own spaces or known reference territories, where the victims are always identifiable, precisely because they are located in real time by technological means, while the perpetrator is usually elusive, hidden, not always localized, and tending to be increasingly artificially intelligent; mostly immune to potential sanctions and punishment. The audience, however, always appears receptive, but unaware, often lacking and incapable of reactive dignity; and where it does appear truly perceptive, it is at best consumed by impotence and resentment. It then comes to mind that "the medium is the message" applies to all media, leading to the conclusion that McLuhan's warning was not coined by chance, but was a warning for the future "global village," which he had already glimpsed in his time. More generally, the constraints for the treatment of a hypothesized *The society of total control*, to which our times seem to be tending, with the risk of becoming *heterodirected and heterodetermined*, and potentially leading to a consequent *collective social pathology*, does not appear to be technical or scientific, but rather eminently value-based, political, ethical, economic, and social. This leads to the final (unresolved) question of removing constraints and who can or should be responsible for researching, identifying, and treating the detected or detectable social pathology.

1. Introduction

Without having to go back and bring up Konrad Lorenz's research on animal behavior and territorial mapping, the close connection, existing in general in human society, between conflict and territoriality is, in our days, clear for all to see: through the Israeli-Palestinian war, as well as the war between Russia and Ukraine. But these specific cases imply a sort of right of surface claimed by the parties in conflict on portions of the planet's crust, almost forgetting the contents of those Scriptures, sometimes cited as justification for that *presumed right of surface* [1] .

If we were to refer below to purely territorial urban phenomena, in the common sense of the term, research coming from interviews with city elites and discussions with residents of negatively and symbolically “branded” marginal settlements [2], would reveal that precisely because of the branding:

- I) a strong identification is created between the territory and its residents, whether they are elite or marginal layers of the urban fabric;
- II) while the latter (i.e. the marginalized) internalize stigmatizing discourses, resist by building counter-narratives, tending to portray their territories as “good places (to live) for poor citizens”, thus creating a positive image of their neighborhoods in the context of often extreme spatial and environmental conditions;
- III) socio-economic marginalization is therefore encouraged and thus the opposition to the elite classes, for whom the stigmatized are necessary, but not desired;
- IV) on the other hand, the stigmatized, aware of their precariousness and the insecurities of their territorial possession, build strong solidarities among themselves that can fuel types of structural violence, in forms of metropolitan ghetto revolt.

More generally, the connection between territory and conflict in society becomes even more profound if we generalize the concept of territory, even applying it to the urban context, but without any limitation to spaces of other natures or dimensions (physical or metaphysical). As we will see below, with the generalization for sociometric purposes, any point in a territory belonging to a multidimensional space with (n) dimensions can be identified and traced through (n) values of variables, numerical or qualitative, in a matrix. Therefore, the notion of territory can be attributed to any space; for example, political, mental, cultural, industrial, economic, scientific, or cyberspace, in which—given the presence of individuals and/or groups—competition arises to prevail and assume hegemonic position in that particular space. This competition, deviating from shared values, can be a precursor to conflict. In this way, labelling and stigma, especially in crowded and dense spaces, can be traced back to a tool and interpreted as functional to the conflict itself in order to assume a hegemonic position in one's own space of reference, thus contributing to the emergence of a wider social pathology. A pathology that must be researched in order to intervene and cure a society in crisis, degenerate, and forgetful of its founding values. It is necessary to reflect, however, on how in the era of *Artificial Intelligence* (AI), the WEB, i.e. the Internet, or in any case “cut out” portions of it, can be considered, even more so in a metropolitan environment, a “territory” in which the labelling that generates stigmatisation is carried out. A process that by changing sign and turning it positive, in content and purpose, can instead prove to be successful, casual or predetermined, for a possibly targeted “target” [3]. In any case, if what P. Bourdieu—listed among the references to consider—says about symbolic power is true, namely, that symbolic power is the primary objective of social life (understood as the struggle “to conquer everything that, in the social world, it confers: credit and appreciation, knowledge and recognition, name, fame, prestige, honor, glory, authority, etc.), it is practically proven that labeling and stigma can have their origins in social conflict. Ultimately, power, even as an intangible symbolic-cultural construct, produces concrete effects in social reality.

2. From Simmel to Goffman

Beyond its possible and controlled use for the opportunistic identification of deviance (e.g. simulative infiltration [4]), stigmatization, or social stigma, appears to be a growing phenomenon in modern computerized society and particularly in urban society. That is, it grows in those segments of society that are distinguished by their social stratification and the high number of interactions

between their members. This stigma consists in attributing a connotation to a member (or a group, territory, institution, etc.) of the community, not only in order to identify and recognize him as the bearer of a certain attribute (usually negative), but more often with the aim of downgrading him to a lower level, with well-defined purposes, including political, productive, cultural and in any case socially relevant purposes.

In the social sciences, labelling or using a label means describing someone or something in a word or a short phrase. We could even assume that the entire language is the result of an extensive labelling process that has continued throughout human history. That is, we are dealing with a natural process of thought and language that does not necessarily imply a positive or negative sign or value. For example, the label "deviant" (literally: that changes way, de-via!) could also be used in a "neutral" way to describe a fact, someone or something that deviates from a path, from a custom, from a norm, without explicitly attributing a value notation to it. While, on the contrary, it is believed that the labelling theory is a sociological theory that pertains to the control and identification of deviant behaviour, in the sense of a serious infringement of the law and even of a precursory stage of mental illness [5]. It seems, therefore, that it is the connection and choice of positive/negative sign, the modality (public/private, friendly/unloving, etc.), and above all the functional use (benevolent/malevolent) made of it that transforms labeling into stigmatization, and thus the simple label attributed into social stigma. One could thus speak of a valence or sign (+/-) of labeling.

Stigmatization, moreover, can be subjected to a metric, for example, along a scale that can go beyond criticism: warning, reprimand, ostracism... and can become disapproval, deprecation, deploration, blame, censure, condemnation. The same, in terms of the possibility of a metric, applies to the way in which stigmatization is implemented, as well as to the purposes for which it is intended. This appears necessary for discernment and judgment.

Typical examples of stigma include racism based on ethnic or gender differences, sexual orientation, or illness, such as mental illness in general and HIV in particular; or the use of substances (performance enhancing drugs, vaccines, etc.), obesity, or religious affiliation. Today, we are witnessing the instrumental use of labeling and stigmatization, which are not necessarily based on objective attributes, but which nevertheless emerge publicly as a product or byproduct of social tensions and conflicts within a more or less large group. Or they emerge through deliberate intent, using appropriate techniques aimed at achieving a specific goal (e.g., *media labeling campaigns* for political or marketing purposes, to subtly discriminate against groups, products, processes, etc.). In any case, group dynamics and sociometry, as will be discussed in more detail below, can be helpful in investigating this issue.

There is, therefore, a close connection, transitive in both directions, between labeling and stigmatization. As a first approximation, it can be assumed that stigmas are typically attributed intentionally or unintentionally and that, when observed and attributed to others by a member of a group, especially a dominant one – but not necessarily a majority one – they can lead, under certain social dynamics, to labeling, stereotyping, exclusion, loss of status, and discrimination. Labeling and stereotyping involve the recognition of differences and their use (deliberate or unconscious) to assign social relevance to those differences. Among the dynamics that can amplify labeling and stigmatization are phenomena induced within the group that respond to patterns of *dual and opposing polarization*, *provocation*, and *obsessive repetition*, in the media in general and social media in particular, to the point of creating a sort of *sounding board* for publicly propagating the stigmatization or the attribution of a "label." Not to mention, in the case of targeted actions, press articles, social media chats, radio and television debates, conferences and round tables, which through insistent and obsessive repetition give credence to the idea that if you persistently "force"

someone in a certain direction, they will eventually go there! Yet, if we exclude the less cultured fringes, who resort to them mockingly and offensively on social media, with a light heart, they seem to be the most mediocre journalism and the most insignificant politics, incapable of resisting the temptation to use such approaches, in an attempt to broaden their audience and consensus. Even if we want to exclude the use of lies, of which one can almost never be certain, the limited use of fact-checking reported by the media has given rise to a journalism that is at best "approximate", which relies more on the effect of resonance and sensationalism, on scandalism or catastrophism, rather than on the striving towards the ascertainment of the truth, which seems to have become simply the exclusive prerogative of opposing "fan groups", only as a function of their group membership. The coining of the term "*fake news*" has itself become a tool of labelling and stigma, rather than an invitation to verify the reliability and veracity of the facts. From a philosophical point of view, even the notion of Science, forgetting its intrinsic characteristic of "Popperian falsifiability" [6], and by resorting to the effects of media resonance, seems to have become subject to the rules of the media and the majority, beyond its essential requirement of necessarily experimental evidence, replaced rather often by hypotheses or theoretical conjectures in which experimentation is completely lacking, if not even absent. From a true scientific point of view, however, we know that physical reality at the Planck scale (atomic and sub-atomic, but not only) is not dominated by the continuum, but by the discrete; not by determinism, but by probabilism; that is, certainty is excluded, as quantum mechanics shows. In the tendency to develop a quantum *metaphysics alongside quantum physics* [7], albeit with critical/didactic purposes, one could dare to assume that Science and Faith are irreconcilable since they operate on different domains. Science is aimed at being in its material dimension; Faith is aimed at being in its spiritual dimension; but in any case on different domains, even in a mathematical sense, that is, in the sense of fields of existence. Given the uniqueness of being, at most, Science and Faith, if viewed in their historicized tendency, can be considered asymptotically proximal in the individual and social cognitive space, always however with margins of uncertainty present, but certainly not superimposable. Thus, despite the separation of fields between Science and Faith, forgetting the compelling promise of genuine dialogue between them, if Science were to be fully embraced in matters of Faith, one could arrive in the Ecclesiastical seat at *hypothesizing and promulgating certainties that would make the Infallible Fallible* [8]. Likewise, a Science based on fideism, a temptation to which our time full of conflicts aimed at hegemony is exposed, would become useless without experimental verification, when the experiment became an "approximation" necessary to overcome purely administrative constraints. Labeling and stigma can therefore become instruments of conflict, sparing even the "highest" fields of human inquiry such as Science and Faith, which are far from subject to majority rule. Yet, to paraphrase *C. Wright Mills*, such a methodological approach of field delimitation, aimed at research, although it resembles the spiritual condition of the *Wobbly*, that is, a *non-aligned man, who takes orders only from himself, often in a situation devoid of reference, who does not like leaders, communists or capitalists*, can be destroyed by labeling and stigma along with its bearer, since *it displeases God and his enemies*. Where God is understood here in the Orwellian sense, that is, *God is Power*, and by reversibility: *Power is God*. Ultimately, it is not laziness, but "non-aligned" research that is not permitted. There is the obligation to choose and the right to make mistakes, but not to abstain and criticize freely, under penalty of labelling and consequent stigma, with the ruin of one's career, family, and future [9].

It can be conceptualized that, in a society or segment of it, stigma arises when two interrelated components are involved: a) human differences are distinguished and labeled; b) a social agent, usually belonging to the dominant culture, links the labeled individual to negative attributes and/or stereotypes. This process can be triggered by a generic social agent who identifies as "rejecting the deviant," and subsequently takes on a collective dimension. Beyond the *rejection of the deviant or the different*, that is, the *pathological*, "territorial" labeling and stigmatization, in the traditional sense described above, although found to a greater extent and not exclusively in urban societies, can

be interpreted as part of a broader phenomenon pertaining to social conflict in general and, in particular, to the struggle for social advancement, to "territorial" hegemony, where the notion of territory can be any space; for example, political, mental, cultural, industrial, economic, scientific, or cyberspace. This is especially evident in stratified societies such as urban, industrial, and post-industrial ones, which emerge in our time, in a competitive environment driven by the centralization of resources on the one hand, and marginalization on the other. This could potentially lead to a clash between a narrow minority, the ruling elite, and a neglected and effectively marginalized majority, excluded, defeated, deprived, and reduced to powerlessness. The constant warnings about the disappearance of the middle class, which functions as a social buffer, and the growing impoverishment and expansion of the most disadvantaged classes, suggest the possibility that such a clash could be desired and planned, with certainty of its outcome, thanks to the wielding of force by an elite minority with decision-making powers. Be it public or private, power is acquired indirectly through the pervasiveness of democracies, if public; it is acquired through the exercise of economic power, if private. All this ignores the fact that the use of force can only be legitimized by its use for the common good; of all society and not just a part of it.

According to a Thomistic logic there can be no *lectio* without *questio* [10], and consequently without *disputatio*. In the specific case under examination the *questio* has been enclosed in the question that investigates whether labelling and stigmatisation cannot be traced back to the conflict taking place in today's society; a conflict that is born, fed and consumed mainly in cyberspace. This is done in order to trace its causes, at least tentatively. In this regard one can try, for example, to make use of a metric derived from Simmel's work on Metropolises and the Life of the Spirit [11]. This can lead to confirming the explanatory reasons not only of the *blasé type* (identified by Simmel), but can be extended to labelling and stigmatisation as aberrant outlets of the enormous growth in the number of social interactions thanks to the media and to "growth" (territorial, economic, demographic, cyber etc.); as can typically happen in a competitive metropolitan environment. Without forgetting that although the notion of *blasé* is, in practice, a tool for identifying and explaining the ways and causes of development in crowded and stratified urban contexts, it can also be understood as a *label* heralding a pathological evolution and thus transformed into a *stigma* with not entirely acceptable purposes. Namely, to negatively brand someone and exclude them from competitive environments; a practice that now seems to pervade every sector, even industrial or traditionally productive ones.

Precisely from the Simmelian analysis of the metropolitan, competitive, structured and hierarchical environment, the following observations can be drawn, which invite us to consider how the labelling and stigmatisation activity is not only the result of individual interactions, but of groups, with their own typical laws [12]:

- a. The intuition according to which social relationships form temporal or permanent units (e.g. groups, associations, professional and non-professional orders, etc.) defining and informing them into a "new entity" (i.e. the group of (n) interacting elements taken as a whole), not simply deriving from the sum of its parts, or of the single individuals who shape such units.
- b. While the laws for each element of the group cause the interactions to vary linearly, those of the group as a whole vary with at least a quadratic law, as if the group were an entity autonomous from the individuals and equipped with its own laws.
- c. The idea that the larger the group, the more the individual is able to express himself; the smaller it is, the fewer opportunities there will be for the individual to differentiate himself, finds evidence in the direct proportion with the interactions that develop, both between the individual members of the group and within the group as a whole.

- d. From the perspective of an evolutionary dynamic of society, the recognition seems to emerge that the laws governing its *metamorphism* are independent of the single individuals that compose it, but find their genesis in the preponderant forces of society itself (as well as historical heritage, external culture, technology, etc.).
- e. The disparity between an individual law of linear progression of interactions and a law that is at least quadratic for the group or for society in general, understood as a group, seems to confirm that the individual, rather than the preservation of his or her own individuality, is in fact forced into an overriding evolution. Ultimately, the preservation of one's individuality clashes with an overriding evolution imposed socially, and in fact.

Furthermore, according to a Simmelian vision [13], social interaction is the foundation of not only social value, since it connects, coagulates and holds together by stabilizing, but also economic value and is concretized in the exchange in terms of "sacrifice" in function of the desired good. This raises the further *question of whether in a society that refuses sacrifice for the desired good it can still be considered a bearer and generator of values*.

Finally, in Simmel, conflict is a fundamental form of social interaction. It necessarily involves at least two parties and stems from the transitivity and reciprocity of the original relationship itself, where the interacting parties are an *Ego* and an *Alter*; where the need arises to discern whether the other is a resource or a problem for each of them. Yet, this discernment, today, is often omitted out of pure prejudice or mistrust.

It can be reasonably conjectured that in a not too distant past a cohesive and cooperative society could ideally be identified by *Iustitia fundamentum regni*; to the point that that justice was at the same time an expression of stability and social security; so that from this derived an *Iustitia erga subditos melior est quam multitudo exercitum*, a concept that historically may have played some role in the opening to democratic systems on the part of the old absolute monarchies.

The cooperative attitude of a harmonious society, however, evolves and changes over time as a function of the vicissitudes, interrelationships, and difficulties that society is forced to face due to *de facto* circumstances, its own choices, or external constraints from which it is unable to free itself, in one way or another. The prolonged absence of social justice, verifiable and even measurable through the loss of cohesion on the one hand and the prevalence of conflict on the other, as well as the manifest impunity of oppressive and deviant behavior by individuals and groups, can constitute labeling and stigmatization as general techniques *ad excludendum*, used in social conflict aimed at scaling up those same oppressive individuals and groups. This leads to the possibility of interpreting labelling and stigmatisation as lucrative, pervasive techniques of a degenerate society, which has lost the paths of cooperation and merit, establishing competition, conflict, abuse, impunity, and ultimately force, as an opportunistic instrument *ad imperandum*, faced with the need to recognise, instead, that "*Non omnes apti sunt ad imperandum*", especially in moments of structural crisis of a partially and poorly globalised society.

It's hard to deny that "organic solidarity" in the Durkheimian sense—that is, referring to the bonds typical of industrial societies, as opposed to "mechanical solidarity" that refers to the bonds existing in pre-industrial communities—appears to be disappearing. It seems to be replaced by an obsessive invitation to individual "giving," which is omnipresent in our society. This is evident not only through the example of people leaving small change (or their "daily groceries") for the migrant on the corner of supermarkets, bars, or city centers, but also through the countless charitable and solidarity organizations that have sprung up almost everywhere, on the internet and social media, and even in banks at ATMs. Veritable marketing operations aimed at "voluntary and targeted" assistance and cooperation projects are becoming pervasive throughout society, to the point of

raising malicious suspicions of a " *back office* " activity of a completely different nature and purpose than those advertised.

The idea of a higher-order social organicism (based, for example, on the concepts of people, society, state, nation, school, church, family, etc.) seems to be disappearing under apparent widespread adverse attack, resulting in the transfer of attributions, once proper to the highest order, to the individual social agent. This individual, alone and against his will, can only gather them and try to keep them alive in socially fundamental organisms that still manage to subsist despite the attacks (the group, associations, family, parish, friendship circles, social *media followers* , etc.). In this context of defunct solidarism, *Labeling & Stigma* can, at least presumptively, be understood as a social pathology, even in the sense of Wright Mills, identifying the sociologist as a social pathologist, through which to trace the causes of the loss of organic solidarity as a lost good. But in this regard, a correlation needs to be identified to provide evidence from the field; perhaps through structured research? Some research has reached conclusions that highlight how stigmatizing labels are commonly used by relatives and friends of patients with serious mental illnesses and these cause considerable discomfort to the patients. From this they draw the need to make society aware of the need to stop the use of these derogatory labels. Along this path it is evident that the distance between the sociologist and the social pathologist is short. To understand how *Labeling & Stigma* can be assumed as a social pathology, especially urban, according to a Wright-Millian logic, it is necessary to take into consideration how the majority of problems (and frequencies of events, in statistical terms) *arise from the deterioration that occurs in the urban context, of a series of values capable of living genuinely in communities of primary groups legitimized by the Christian and Jeffersonian tradition* . [14] For an ideal organic village, «the whole world should have been an enlarged, Christian democratic version of a rural village» [15] . In this logic, however, socio-economic stratification also plays its part. In fact:

«Social distance is a cruel fact, internalized with difficulty, and deplored as profoundly contrary to the ideals, not to say immoral, in our Christian tradition. It is not enough to have saints, we must have the "communion" of saints. To have social relations, we must 'sniff' each other. The aspiration to preserve stable values and arrangements, inspired by rural culture, is indicated by the implicit model used to detect urban disorganization; and it is also evident in the emphasis placed on the well-being of the *community* . This is assumed as a superior unity, and often represents the aim of the problematic interest.» [16] .

The connection between social pathology (*Labeling & Stigma* in this case) and the underlying value notation thus appears evident: the values above are well expressed and recognizable.

Some conceptualizations, from other research, explicitly imply the idea that stigma depends entirely on social, economic and political power. See the research in sociology of work from the 70s by F. Ferrarotti in North American society. They clearly indicate the reasons present in the selection of the managerial class [17] . Selection based on competence only at low and medium levels, reserving and making the highest positions dependent on social membership to elite or family groups , and on connivance with interests shared with the dominant classes . Today large companies consult the individual profiles on social media of those they consider suitable to take on productive roles, not only managerial ones. Taking all this into account and adequately tying everything together, we can prefigure what role a targeted labelling and stigmatisation action can have in the selection of the managerial class in a society that has lost not only organic solidarity, but also respect for merit, competence, and its own founding values, including the recognition of objective truth. If this occurs in certain managerial roles, we can imagine, not just in imagination, what could happen—and is actually happening, as recent events demonstrate—in the selection of the political, managerial, healthcare, and academic classes, to name just a few examples. Therefore, it is no longer just a matter of sociology for the social pathology oriented toward deviance and

ultimately security, but a genuine need for social research to outline strategies functional to the survival of a society in crisis: the Western one, which has lost, by deviating as a whole, from its founding orientations and values of self-determination, consensus, and democracy free from interfering external constraints. Perhaps we should rediscover the myth of social pathology that was forced and relegated to marginal positions after the past student uprisings and the metropolitan ghettos, phenomena that are similarly resurfacing today. Ultimately, it is a question of rediscovering a serious critique of the *power establishment in its entirety*, whether autocratic or democratic, beyond any partisan alignment, in the belief that the sociologist's mission must play a critical public role, rather than adhering to pseudo-scientific positions, ready to negotiate the elevation of one's own status in exchange for a renunciation of one's own "ideological apologia".

Today, considering what is happening in the world, it would be really necessary, especially in academic circles, to continue to question and delve deeper into the «(...) impossibility of considering sociology a science devoid of the characteristics presupposed as its own, that is, objective and free from values» [18]. The *Weberian value-free nature* which is objectified in the *ideal typical framework*, recomposed by the researcher in the course of his research, beyond its effectiveness as an instrument of analysis of reality, can only assume, at best, a probabilistic value, with the possibility of proving to be realistic, but not real. Therefore, the conclusions of any social pathologist should be taken into serious consideration and analysed, evaluated, but not mistaken for certainties, nor should they claim to be considered as such. If a snapshot of the paths of fideistic choices were possible, we could find some priest, rabbi, or imam, etc., acting as social pathologist, with ranges of action confined to their own limited territorial areas. But, on the paths of secular, agnostic or global materialist choices, even if we came across an unlikely and spurious "social pathologist", would we find a sociologist? And above all, if we did find one, in the observational evidence from his perspective, would he consider that "change has its foundation in continuity and the real problem is that of saving values as the only concrete perspective of the individual", thus ultimately taking the observed outcome or tendency for granted? Or by de-historicising the observational context, would he be able to highlight the signs and possibilities of change to indicate its opportunities or risks? The complexity of the situation, its prospective indecipherability and the need for intervention, would ultimately end up referring everything to the responsibility of politics, which in the rediscovery that "*science is doubt*" would find justifications in precautionary approaches emerging from a constitutionalised precautionary principle [19].

3. Labeling, Stigma, and Sociometry

Sociometry is a way to measure, within a network however limited, the ways and degrees to which people—that is, the nodes that form that network—relate to each other. It enables the development of an analysis and counting of vectors, that is, the segments connecting one node to another (e.g., positive, negative, or neutral). Such measures of *relatability* can be useful not only in assessing behavior within groups, but also in comparing them between groups; as well as in implementing assessment, control, or change interventions; and, for example, determining the extent of change. For a group or its management or responsibility, sociometry can also be a useful tool for reducing conflict (and specifically stigmatization) and thus improving communication and safety, because it allows the group to see itself and reflect objectively following an analysis of its own dynamics and characteristics. It is also a powerful tool for assessing changes over time, space, and situation, and thus the dynamics and developmental trends in groups of different natures and dedicated to different objectives. The above-mentioned generalization of the concept of territory could also be significant for sociometric purposes. Any point of a territory belonging to a multidimensional space with (n) dimensions can be identified and traced through (n) values of variables, numerical or qualitative, in a matrix. The same applies to any node and the related vectors of a network that

develops in (n) dimensions. The evolutions of (n) nodes of a network (therefore of a group, or subgroup, in this case affected by phenomena of labelling and stigmatization), as well as the parameters that express a measure of it, can be monitored in real time. The information and computational technologies associated with a network, thanks to real-time tracking, have no difficulty in concretely realizing the configurations necessary for this; they already do so for the analysis of so-called *big data* ! In other words, one could conclude that a multidimensional network is a network in which there can be multiple and different qualitative and quantitative relationships between the nodes [20] .

It's clear that when analyzing any network affected by labeling phenomena (and the resulting stigma), node density and network density, for example, can be *drivers* for research or simple in-depth analysis. If further investigation reveals the existence of links between the nodes that generate labeling vectors, it could lead to the identification of potential cliques and, from there, the identification of a common direction.

There's no doubt that technology is significantly advancing sociometry as a whole, becoming a multidisciplinary scientific tool for investigation in diverse fields—think, for example, of security, prevention, and anti-mafia; but also of marketing, psychology, and psychiatry. The point is that, like all technology, even online technology, along with its devices, tools, procedures, methods, and so on, is neither good nor bad; it's neutral! So, much like labeling, the value notation (+/-; positive/negative) it contains is crucial for stigmatization: everything depends on how it's used, for what purposes, and with what results for the individual, the group, and society as a whole. Monitoring, social control, and corrective action on such practices emerging from the media, *social media* , and beyond, are now technologically possible and, one might argue, are already underway. The constraints on implementing research, however, and on treating this specific social pathology, are certainly not technical-scientific, but eminently political, ethical, economic, and social.

4. Goffman's metaphor of theatrical representation and McLuhan's warning

Adopting Goffman's metaphor of theatrical performance, in today's highly computerized, media-infused, and artificially intelligent society of spectacle and consumption, labeling and stigmatization can ultimately be seen as a "public spectacle." Three subjects always participate: a *victim* , a *perpetrator* , and an *audience* . The spectacle unfolds publicly, before the eyes of a territorialized and localized *audience* , dispersed across its own known reference spaces, where the *victims* are always identifiable, precisely because they are located in real time by technology. Meanwhile, the *perpetrator* is usually elusive, hidden, not always localized, and tends to be artificially intelligent; and for the most part immune, de facto, unpunished and unpunishable, tough in the face of potential sanctions and penalties. Sometimes the *perpetrator* (material executor) may simply be a *mandate* that conceals the true *instigator* , who would be difficult to trace, without appropriate means, if it were simply a *software program* that activates a procedure; for example, of *Artificial Intelligence* . The *audience* , on the other hand, always appears receptive, but unaware (almost under the narcotic effect of the *medium* used), often lacking and incapable of reactive dignity; and where it appears truly perceptive, at most it is consumed by impotence and resentment. Then it comes to mind that the "*medium is the message*" is valid for all media, to conclude that this warning by McLuhan was not coined by chance, but was a warning for the future "*global village*" , which he had already glimpsed in his time [21] and which we are experiencing today.

5. Conclusions

In an era in which literature speaks of *surveillance capitalism* , *capitalism without capital* , *total control* aimed at a *new frontier of power* , the broadening of the notion of "territory" and its

connection to “nine-dimensional spaces” also broadens the meaning of “labeling” and “stigmatization,” taking on a much more general and pervasive phenomenal configuration, typical of our urbanized, stratified and computerized times, to the point of being able to draw a link with the notion of “social pathology,” potentially treatable in qualitative and quantitative sociometric terms.

If you look closely, each of the greats of sociology, including, to name a few for example:

- Herbert Spencer through the idea of Darwinism and social organicism, which conceived of hierarchically structured societies, industrial or military;
- Thorstein Veblen through the theory of the leisure class, who wrote critically of conspicuous waste, and of consumerism as a function of social stratification;
- Émile Durkheim through the concept of anomie, the connections between suicide and social structure, and the degree of integration into it;
- Max Weber, through the analysis of power (charismatic, bureaucratic, military, etc.), in its various manifestations and consequences, as well as the spirit of capitalism and the underlying Protestant ethic, as well as the value-free attitude in the social sciences and in the intellectual profession;
- Georg Simmel, through social interaction as the origin of sociation and social binder, as well as through the exposé of the psychology and philosophy of money in modern society;
- Herbert Marcuse through *the one-dimensional man*, and the idea that individual happiness could not be separated from the creation of a rational society;
- Talcott Parsons through the theory of social action and *structural-functionalism*, as well as the idea that human personality is not innate, but created through the process of socialization, where *the primary agent* is the family;
- Erving Goffman through the metaphor of theatrical representation and *symbolic interactionism*, underpinned by the idea that social interaction constantly engages in the process of "impression management", in which each agent tries to present and behave in order to avoid embarrassment for himself or others;

have had, each in their own way and according to their own point of view, perception of aspects highlighting some sort of possible social pathology, although their warning, despite being studied, transmitted and preserved over time, seems never to have found effective and decisive applications carried out, in concrete terms, in society and in social policies, with the aim of curing the pathology detected. Furthermore, although each has grasped a part of the profound aspects of social reality, the overall picture to be composed, with a holistic approach, and in the manner of a puzzle, does not appear complete and seems to remain in a state of fragmentation and incompleteness without a real unifying theory, as pursued in vain by a European sociological tradition. This cannot be said, however, of North American sociology which, through sociometry, thanks to Moreno [22] and subsequent developments, above all thanks to mathematics and computer technology, has allowed the development of totalizing, organic and multidisciplinary investigation tools. Today, they are potentially capable of researching and conducting study, monitoring, social control, and corrective action, not only on aspects of *labeling and stigma*, but on any social variable, both qualitative and quantitative, through the *web*, the media, and *social media* in particular. This has led to our time being defined as *a society of total control*, potentially heterodirected and heterodetermined, where primitive organic solidarity and normative consensus for social action have disappeared, replaced and left at the mercy of individual relativism, potentially affected by irrationality, indecision, loss of

identity, and error. All of this promotes states of anxiety and a genuine fear of the future, potentially leading to a collective social pathology.

Is it radical pessimism, social catastrophism, erroneous visionaryism, or transitory and inconsistent conjectures? The future will tell! However, we seem to be witnessing the spread of *structural anomie*, a social condition of *uprooting from a culture of origin and the collapse of normal moral values* (in a statistical sense) or simple criteria guiding individuals. Meanwhile, national and supranational regulatory frameworks, including that of Human Rights, are developing and becoming more complex, but they are clashing in practice and results with a reality in which, due to attitudes of *libertarian tolerance* and *persistent impunity* towards any form of transgression, such attitudes are even becoming a compensatory ideology, supported by the perception of widespread injustice.

Furthermore, this *lost identity* and *structural anomie* seems to evolve from the conflict between value and belief systems, causing the compromise of social bonds between individuals, groups, institutions and their communities. Evidence of this, in all social strata, is provided by: the widespread sense of precariousness, indecision, confusion, humiliation, depression, abandonment, and lost values, including the value of identity and human life forced into "alphanumeric codes" [23]; as well as the generalized conflict (economic, monetary, social, cultural, military, generational, etc.) in quasi-structural forms, interpretable as functional to a dying society, which thinks of Force (or worse of "Police States" [24] !) as a tool for the management and survival of existing forms of domination, of which *Label & Stigma* are an integral part. Recognizing that the constraints for research, implementation and treatment of social pathology in specific or determinable cases are certainly not technical-scientific, but eminently value-based, political, ethical, economic, social, the *question* that arises is the following: is there a cure and a possible primary agent to identify and practice it after having dissolved the existing constraints? And can we be certain that the "patient" (individual, group, or society) would accept treatment and be cured? Or rather, falling back on Simmelian conclusions, does it seem confirmed that the individual social agent, rather than the preservation of his own individuality, is in fact forced by an overriding evolution that he, as an individual, cannot control? Ultimately, the preservation of one's individuality—and with it the choice of one's own reference values—clash with a predominant socially imposed evolution, and in fact, over which the individual social agent can at best exert a negligible influence, but which he certainly cannot direct or determine, since he would clash, in an unequal conflict, with the preponderant forces of society itself.

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See <https://zenodo.org/records/764778>

References & Notes

[1] In fact, it is no coincidence that Leviticus 25:23-24 states: “²³The land may not be sold in perpetuity, for the land is mine, and you are strangers and sojourners with me.²⁴Therefore you shall grant redemption rights for the land in all the land that you possess.” Furthermore, it speaks of possession and not of ownership. Possession and ownership are not synonymous, but very different concepts.

[2] AA.VV. "They say these are places for criminals, but this is our home":<https://www.liverpooluniversitypress.co.uk/doi/10.3828/idpr.2021.9>

[3] An example can be cited that real estate market operators could confirm: the continuous and persistent association of a "normal" urban area with positive attributes (e.g.: quiet, clean, well-kept, renovated, civilized, respectable, elegant, *green*, etc.), to the point of producing a widespread and lasting sharing of those attributes, increases demand and favors higher house prices and rents in that area. This confirms that: *if you "force" someone insistently in a certain direction, in the end they will go there!*

[4] Police intrusion for *intelligence* into any group (even in the *deep web*) can be done *online*, now in *remote mode* and *smart working* and without the traditional dangers for the intruder.

[5] « Evidence from modified labeling theory and other approaches to labeling, stereotyping, and rejection strongly suggests that the negative consequences associated (...) are experienced by many people. An emerging social phenomenon that is likely to change causal attributions of mental illness is the genetic revolution. ». See:<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/handbook-for-the-study-of-mental-health/labeling-and-stigma/A396E399CEE0960B2103B7D75EF0599D>

[6] P. Pellecchia (PUL) – THE POPPERIANS AND THE SCIENTIFIC REVOLUTIONS – Ed. S. Germano – Cassino – 1986

[7] Quantum Metaphysics – Sven Ortoli and Jaean-Pierre Pharabod – Castelvechchio Editore – 2013 – ISBN 978-88-7615- 822-3

[8] See Can. 747 - §1 of the CODE OF CANON LAW - Book III - The Teaching Function of the Church

[9] If all this should recall events of our time of a young and brilliant sociologist, an academic at an elite university, the reference is purely coincidental.

[10] Pasquale Pellecchia – Pontifical Lateran University – THE CURRENTNESS OF THE DIDACTIC AND CULTURAL APPROACH OF ST. THOMAS AQUINAS – Tip. Edit. Pasquarelli – Sora – Part one – See the link between *questio*, *lectio* and *disputatio*.

- [11] See the Appendix of the research in <https://zenodo.org/records/764778> - R.Morelli - SUSTAINABILITY AND VALUES RECONSIDERING SIMMEL - An opportunity to also reflect on the transition from Total Cost Management (TCM) to Systemic Value Management (SVM)
- [12] See note 11
- [13] See G.Simmel - PHILOSOPHY OF MONEY – UTET Publisher (2013) as well as G.Simmel - METROPOLIS AND THE LIFE OF THE SPIRIT – edited by P. Jedloowski - Classics of Sociology – Armando Publisher – 2005 - The very short essay taken into consideration here, rightly recognised as a classic text useful for reflection on the relationship between modernity and metropolis, offers ideas that go well beyond these areas (and can be found at the following link: [simmel - le metropoli e la vita dello spirito.pdf \(leoneg.it\)](#)).
- [14] C.Wright Mills – THE MYTH OF SOCIAL PATHOLOGY – Armando Editore – Classics of Sociology – Edited and with a preface by R.Rauty – 2001 – ISBN 88-8358-276-4 - pages 62 and following.
- [15] Idem, as above.
- [16] Idem, as above.
- [17] F. Ferrarotti - Degree Course in Sociology – University of Rome - SOCIOLOGY OF WORK – Lectures – ELIA Publishing House – Rome 1974
- [18] Introduction by Raffaele Rauty to THE MYTH OF SOCIAL PATHOLOGY by C.Wright Mills published by Armando Editore in the Sociology Classics series – 2001 – ISBN 88-8358-276-4 page 12
- [19] The Maastricht Treaty introduced the precautionary principle (taken from the European Constitution art. III-233[5]) currently set out in art. 191 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union.
- [20] University of Pisa - Department of Computer Science - PhD in Computer Science - Ph.D. Thesis - Multidimensional Network Analysis - Michele Coscia. See <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/14704618.pdf>
- [21] M.McLuhan – THE TOOLS OF COMMUNICATING – SDS – Garzanti Editore -1966
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